

Key Concepts: Personality Disorder

INTRODUCTION DSM lists personality disorder by ill example and lists it not abstract enough to work in terra incognita.

PURPOSE This article purposes to list personality disorder by healthy example and to list it abstract enough to work in terra incognita to purpose less false-positives for transcultural patients compared to the DSM list.

METHODS The method is snowball sampling.

RESULTS The work started with the metaphor paintbrush grip which is necessary in order to paint. Personality disorder is disintegrality and integrality is first-person, precise, respect, responsible, and valid. For the practical aspects of first-person, (non)inertial reference frame is optional. This (non)inertial reference frame is sourced from physics. For the concepts precise and valid, these are sourced from epidemiology. For the concept responsible with its different extends, this is sourced from psychiatrist Helberg: “In that relation: I have 50% responsibility and you have 50% responsibility to make this work, but I have 100% responsibility for my 50%.”. For the concept respect, an abstract definition could be that where responsible is about active voting rights respect is about passive voting rights.

DISCUSSION The result lists five parts and these could be compared with the three parts of the DSM list which are cluster A, - B, and - C. If first-person is found to be a new cluster, then inclusion - and exclusion of dissociative disorder in personality disorder could be discussed. Furthermore, it could be compared with the four parts of the ALLEA list about research integrity which are reliability, honesty, respect, accountability.

References

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Data provenance (transactional-level)

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